

COVID-19 VACCINATION FOR PREGNANT WOMEN: ANALYSIS OF SAFETY, EFFICACY, AND PERINATAL OUTCOMES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14613934>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th December 2024
Accepted: 30th December 2024
Online: 31th December 2024

KEYWORDS

COVID-19, pregnancy,
vaccination, safety, efficacy,
perinatal outcomes,
immunogenicity.

ABSTRACT

Background. The COVID-19 pandemic poses a significant health risk for pregnant women. Due to physiological immunosuppression during pregnancy, the risk of severe COVID-19 and complications in pregnant women is higher. Thus, studying the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy is a pressing issue. **Aim.** To evaluate the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy and its impact on perinatal outcomes. **Materials and Methods.** The study included 150 pregnant women, 120 of whom were vaccinated against COVID-19, while 30 formed the control group. Vaccinated women were divided into two groups based on their pregnancy term: II and III trimesters. Hemostasis, fetoplacental system, hormones, cytokines, and immunogenicity levels were assessed. Statistical analysis was conducted using significance levels ($p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$). **Results.** Vaccinated women showed normal fetoplacental system and hemostasis indicators. Hormone and cytokine levels remained within physiological limits. IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV-2 were detected in 87% of vaccinated women. IgG titers increased significantly at 3, 6, and 9 months after vaccination. Preterm births were 1.5 times less frequent among vaccinated women compared to unvaccinated ones. The Apgar score for newborns was 8-9 points in most cases. The incidence of respiratory infections among newborns was 1.7 times lower.

ВАКЦИНАЦИЯ БЕРЕМЕННЫХ ЖЕНЩИН ПРОТИВ COVID-19: АНАЛИЗ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ, ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНЫХ ИСХОДОВ

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th December 2024

Accepted: 30th December 2024

Online: 31th December 2024

KEYWORDS

COVID-19, беременность,
вакцинация, безопасность,
эффективность,
перинатальные исходы,
иммуногенность.

ABSTRACT

Актуальность. Пандемия COVID-19 представляет серьёзную угрозу для здоровья беременных женщин. В связи с физиологическим снижением активности иммунной системы во время беременности, риск тяжёлого течения COVID-19 и осложнений у беременных повышен. Поэтому исследование безопасности и эффективности вакцинации беременных женщин против COVID-19 является актуальной задачей. **Цель.** Оценить безопасность и эффективность вакцинации против COVID-19 у беременных женщин, а также её влияние на перинатальные исходы. **Материалы и методы.** В исследовании приняли участие 150 беременных женщин. Из них 120 были вакцинированы против COVID-19, а 30 составили контрольную группу. Вакцинированные женщины были разделены на две группы в зависимости от срока беременности: II и III триместры. В рамках исследования оценивались показатели гемостаза, фетоплацентарной системы, гормонов, цитокинов и уровень иммуногенности. Статистический анализ проводился с использованием уровней значимости ($p < 0,05$, $p < 0,01$, $p < 0,001$). **Результаты.** У вакцинированных женщин показатели фетоплацентарной системы и гемостаза оставались в пределах нормы. Уровни гормонов и цитокинов не выходили за физиологические границы. Антитела IgG к SARS-CoV-2 сформировались у 87% вакцинированных женщин. Уровень титров IgG значительно увеличивался через 3, 6 и 9 месяцев после вакцинации. Преждевременные роды среди вакцинированных женщин наблюдались в 1,5 раза реже, чем у невакцинированных. Состояние новорождённых по шкале Апгар в большинстве случаев оценивалось в 8-9 баллов. Частота респираторных инфекций у новорождённых была на 1,7 раза ниже.

HOMILADOR AYOLLARNI COVID-19 GA QARSHI EMLASH: XAVFSIZLIK, SAMARADORLIK VA PERINATAL NATIJALAR TAHLILI

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th December 2024

Accepted: 30th December 2024

Online: 31th December 2024

KEYWORDS

COVID-19, homiladorlik,
vaksinatsiya, xavfsizlik,
samaradorlik, perinatal
natijalar, immunogenlik.

ABSTRACT

Dolzarbliqi. COVID-19 pandemiyasi homilador ayollar uchun salomatlikka jiddiy xavf tug'dirdi. Homiladorlik davrida organizmdagi immun tizimi susayishi tufayli COVID-19 kasalligi og'ir kechishi va asoratlar xavfi yuqori bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli, homiladorlar uchun vaksinatsiyaning xavfsizligi va samaradorligini o'rganish dolzarb masala hisoblanadi. **Maqsad.** Homiladorlik davrida COVID-19 vaksinatsiyasining xavfsizligi va samaradorligini baholash, shuningdek, perinatal natijalarga ta'sirini aniqlash. **Material va usullar.** Tadqiqotda 150 nafar homilador ayol qatnashdi. Ulardan 120 nafari COVID-19'ga qarshi emlangan, 30 nafari esa emlanmagan nazorat guruhini tashkil qildi. Emlangan ayollar homiladorlikning II va III trimestrlariga ko'ra ikki guruhga ajratildi. Tadqiqot davomida gemostaz tizimi, fetoplatsentar tizim, gormonlar va sitokinlar holati, shuningdek, immunogenlik darajasi baholandi. Natijalar statistik tahlil orqali o'rganildi ($p < 0,05$, $p < 0,01$, $p < 0,001$). **Natijalar.** Emlangan ayollarda fetoplatsentar tizim va gemostaz ko'rsatkichlari me'yor darajasida saqlandi. Gormonlar holati va sitokinlar miqdori fiziologik chegaralardan chiqmagani aniqlandi. Immunogenlik: SARS-CoV-2'ga qarshi IgG antitanachalari 87% holatlarda shakllandi. IgG titr darajasi emlashdan so'ng 3, 6 va 9 oyda oshgani kuzatildi. Akusherlik va perinatal natijalar: Emlangan ayollarda muddatidan oldin tug'ruqlar emlanmaganlarga nisbatan 1,5 marta kam kuzatildi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlar Apgar shkalasiga ko'ra yuqori baholandi. Respirator infeksiyalar holati 1,7 marta kam qayd etildi.

Introduction

The SARS-CoV-2 virus (COVID-19), which emerged at the end of 2019, led to a global pandemic and posed significant challenges to healthcare systems worldwide [1–3]. Throughout the pandemic, the high transmissibility of the virus, the severity of the disease and its complications, as well as various risk factors, created a serious threat to vulnerable groups, particularly pregnant women [4–8].

Pregnancy, as a physiological state, involves a natural weakening of the immune system in the maternal body, which increases susceptibility to infectious diseases. In this context, pregnant women may be at higher risk of contracting COVID-19 and experiencing a more severe clinical course [9–12]. In addition, pregnant women with COVID-19 have been

observed to suffer from various obstetric and perinatal complications, including preeclampsia, preterm birth, hypoxia, and complications during labor. These factors underscore the heightened need to effectively protect pregnant women from the virus, thereby highlighting the importance of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy [13–17].

Nevertheless, concerns regarding the safety, efficacy, and fetal impact of vaccination during pregnancy have been widely debated within the medical community [18–22]. It is crucial to determine how hormonal, immunological, and metabolic changes during pregnancy might alter vaccine effects, and to understand how vaccination may influence obstetric and perinatal outcomes. In particular, further research is needed to assess potential impacts on the fetoplacental system, hemostasis, cytokine levels, and the development of the immune response [23–25].

This article presents research findings on the safety, efficacy, and effects of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy on perinatal outcomes. The study aims to evaluate the significance of vaccination for pregnant women, analyze the current status of the issue, and pave the way for future scientific investigations. The results may serve as a scientific basis for accurately assessing the benefits and risks of vaccination in pregnant women, as well as for developing recommendations to improve postpartum health and perinatal outcomes.

Study Objective to evaluate the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy, and to determine its impact on perinatal outcomes.

Materials and Methods

A total of 150 pregnant women were included in this study, of whom 120 had been vaccinated against COVID-19, and 30 constituted a control group of unvaccinated pregnant women. The 120 pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19 were divided into two main groups according to their gestational age at the time of vaccination: Group I consisted of 60 (40%) pregnant women vaccinated during the second trimester, and Group II consisted of 60 (40%) pregnant women vaccinated during the third trimester. The control group included 30 (20.0%) pregnant women who declined vaccination.

During the study, we investigated the effect of COVID-19 vaccination on obstetric and perinatal indicators in vaccinated pregnant women, including its impact on the fetoplacental system, hemostasis, and cytokine levels. These assessments were performed dynamically at 20, 22, and 24 weeks of gestation in the second trimester, and at 28, 30, and 32 weeks in the third trimester. In addition to general obstetric examinations, the safety and efficacy of the vaccine administered to the vaccinated women were primarily evaluated by assessing the immunogenicity of the vaccine and by analyzing pregnancy and birth outcomes.

Statistical processing of the results was performed using Spearman's rank correlation method in the STATISTICA 10.0 software package and the Epi Info 7.2.2.2 statistical program to identify errors in two interrelated variational series for paired data. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$. Fisher's criterion was employed to test the equality of variances. For groups with equal distributions and normally distributed data, an ANOVA was performed, and Student's t-test for independent samples was used to determine the statistical significance of differences in quantitative indicators.

The reliability of differences between the groups was assessed for independent populations using the nonparametric Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney criterion, as well as through

standard variational statistical methods (Student's t-test and the χ^2 test). To analyze correlations among the studied indicators, a correlation analysis was conducted using Spearman's rank method by calculating the correlation coefficient and subsequently determining its significance with the t-test.

Results

The average age of the women in the study was 24.8 ± 0.39 years. Among those vaccinated against COVID-19, the majority of women in the second trimester (66.7%) and the third trimester (85.0%) were between 20 and 29 years of age. Furthermore, a significantly higher proportion of women in Group I (98.3%) were under 30 years of age, compared to 23.3% in the control group ($p < 0.001$). By age range, most of the women in Groups I and II were of early reproductive age, while 5.0% were of advanced reproductive age (36 years, $p < 0.05$).

To assess the state of the fetoplacental system in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, fetal biometry, Doppler ultrasound studies, and placental hormone levels were investigated. In addition to standard echographic examinations, Doppler ultrasound was performed in all patients to measure hemodynamic parameters of the fetoplacental system, including the resistance index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and the systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D).

In 60 pregnant women from Group I, Doppler ultrasound at 20 weeks of gestation showed normal RI values in the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.37 ± 0.02 , 0.63 ± 0.01 , and 1.31 ± 0.02 , respectively). The PI values were 1.04 ± 0.02 , 1.65 ± 0.04 , and 18.21 ± 0.01 , respectively, while the S/D ratios were 2.5 ± 0.02 , 4.4 ± 0.04 , and 2.8 ± 0.03 , respectively.

In 60 pregnant women from Group II, Doppler ultrasound at 28 weeks of gestation showed normal RI values in the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.34 ± 0.01 , 0.54 ± 0.04 , and 1.52 ± 0.02 , respectively). The PI values were 1.54 ± 0.02 , 1.13 ± 0.01 , and 31.8 ± 0.04 , respectively, while the S/D ratios were 2.2 ± 0.02 , 3.2 ± 0.03 , and 2.2 ± 0.01 , respectively.

In 60 pregnant women from Group I, Doppler ultrasound at 22 weeks of gestation again showed normal RI values in the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.36 ± 0.02 , 0.61 ± 0.01 , and 1.44 ± 0.02 , respectively). The PI values were 0.92 ± 0.02 , 1.17 ± 0.04 , and 20.6 ± 0.01 , respectively, while the S/D ratios were 2.4 ± 0.02 , 4.67 ± 0.04 , and 2.2 ± 0.03 , respectively.

In 60 pregnant women from Group II, Doppler ultrasound at 30 weeks of gestation showed normal RI values in the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.34 ± 0.02 , 0.49 ± 0.01 , and 1.43 ± 0.02 , respectively), as well as elevated PI values (0.52 ± 0.02 , 0.76 ± 0.04 , and 37.2 ± 0.01 , respectively). The S/D ratios were 2.0 ± 0.02 , 3.4 ± 0.04 , and 2.2 ± 0.03 , respectively (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Doppler Metrics of the Fetoplacental System in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19

In the 60 pregnant women in Group I, Doppler ultrasound performed at 24 weeks of gestation revealed resistance index (RI) values within the normal range for the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.35 ± 0.02 , 0.58 ± 0.01 , and 1.50 ± 0.02 , respectively). Elevated pulsatility index (PI) values were recorded (0.78 ± 0.02 , 1.14 ± 0.04 , and 26.3 ± 0.01 , respectively), while the systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D) was 2.3 ± 0.02 , 3.8 ± 0.04 , and 2.8 ± 0.03 , respectively.

In the 60 pregnant women in Group II, Doppler ultrasound performed at 32 weeks of gestation similarly revealed RI values within the normal range for the uterine artery, umbilical artery, and fetal middle cerebral artery (0.33 ± 0.02 , 0.50 ± 0.01 , and 1.44 ± 0.02 , respectively). The PI values were 0.46 ± 0.02 , 0.70 ± 0.04 , and 32.2 ± 0.01 , while the S/D ratios were 2.3 ± 0.02 , 2.9 ± 0.04 , and 2.3 ± 0.03 , respectively.

Comparing these findings with those obtained at equivalent gestational weeks from Doppler ultrasound in the control group (RI: 0.34 ± 0.02 , 0.61 ± 0.01 , 1.33 ± 0.02 ; PI: 0.56 ± 0.02 , 0.58 ± 0.04 , 22.1 ± 0.01 ; S/D: 2.4 ± 0.02 , 3.2 ± 0.04 , 2.3 ± 0.03), no adverse effects of the COVID-19 vaccine on fetoplacental hemodynamic parameters were identified for pregnant women in either of the main study groups.

In addition to examining fetoplacental hemodynamic parameters in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, levels of placental hormones were measured in Group I at 20, 22, and 24 weeks of gestation, and in Group II at 28, 30, and 32 weeks of gestation. In both groups, serum estriol levels increased in accordance with gestational age. Specifically, in Group I, compared to initial values at 20 weeks, estriol levels increased 2.2-fold by 22 and 24 weeks, reaching 2.8 ± 0.06 ng/mL, 4.4 ± 0.08 ng/mL, and 6.4 ± 0.12 ng/mL, respectively ($p < 0.01$). A similar trend was observed in Group II, where estriol levels at 30 and 32 weeks were 1.2 times higher than those at 28 weeks, measuring 6.8 ± 0.15 ng/mL, 7.4 ± 0.18 ng/mL, and 8.6 ± 0.23 ng/mL, respectively ($p < 0.01$).

In vaccinated women from Group I, placental lactogen levels also rose in line with gestational age. Compared to measurements at 20 weeks, placental lactogen levels at 22 and

24 weeks were 1.1 times higher, reaching 4.4 ± 0.16 mg/L, 4.8 ± 0.21 mg/L, and 5.6 ± 0.25 mg/L, respectively ($p < 0.01$). A similar pattern was observed in Group II, where placental lactogen levels measured at 30 and 32 weeks were 1.2 times higher than those at 28 weeks, at 7.1 ± 0.31 mg/L, 8.2 ± 0.36 mg/L, and 9.1 ± 0.39 mg/L, respectively ($p < 0.01$).

Among pregnant women in Group I, who had been vaccinated against coronavirus before pregnancy, serum estradiol levels increased in proportion to gestational age. At 22–24 weeks, these levels were 1.1 times higher than at 20 weeks. Estradiol rose consistently with gestation, reaching 1561.0 ± 18.1 pg/mL at 20 weeks, 1628.0 ± 22.8 pg/mL at 22 weeks, and 1780.5 ± 25.8 pg/mL at 24 weeks ($p < 0.01$). A similar pattern was observed in Group II, where estradiol levels at 30–32 weeks were 1.4 times higher than at 28 weeks, measuring 6525.1 ± 152.7 pg/mL at 28 weeks, 8134.1 ± 170.7 pg/mL at 30 weeks, and 9168.1 ± 193.6 pg/mL at 32 weeks ($p < 0.01$).

Thus, in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, the longitudinal assessment of fetoplacental hormones showed that changes in their serum levels were consistent with advancing gestation, and no negative alterations were observed when comparing different time points and the number of vaccination doses administered ($p < 0.05$).

Furthermore, we analyzed additional markers of the fetoplacental system—trophoblastic glycoprotein (TBG), alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), and chorionic gonadotropin (hCG)—in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19. The findings showed that in Group I, the TBG level at 20 weeks was 2.2 times lower than that at 28 weeks in Group II (35008.4 ± 1021.8 ng/mL vs. 68008.6 ± 1766.0 ng/mL, $p < 0.001$). However, in Group I, TBG increased 1.2 times at 22 and 24 weeks compared to 20 weeks, reaching 44008.0 ± 1492.3 ng/mL and 52018.2 ± 2433.5 ng/mL, respectively. A similar rise was noted in Group II, where TBG levels increased 1.7 times across the assessed weeks, reaching 68008.6 ± 1983.1 ng/mL and 740054.1 ± 2507.3 ng/mL, respectively.

In pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19 in Group I, the serum level of alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) at 20 weeks of gestation was found to be 1.6 times lower compared to the levels at 22 and 24 weeks. The values measured at these weeks were 78.0 ± 2.5 IU/mL, 125.5 ± 2.7 IU/mL, and 132.3 ± 4.0 IU/mL, respectively ($p < 0.001$). A similar trend was observed in Group II, where the AFP levels increased by 1.4 times from 28 weeks to subsequent weeks, measuring 148.0 ± 4.8 IU/mL, 152.2 ± 5.3 IU/mL, and 244.2 ± 6.5 IU/mL at 28, 30, and 32 weeks, respectively.

The analysis of chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) levels in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19 showed a progressive increase in this marker with advancing gestational age in both groups. Specifically, in Group I, the hCG level at 20 weeks of gestation was 1.9 times lower than the levels at 22 and 24 weeks. The values recorded at these weeks were 8099.2 ± 61.2 IU/mL, 8852.1 ± 81.3 IU/mL, and 9244.1 ± 118.9 IU/mL, respectively. In Group II, hCG levels were 1.2 times higher at 30 and 32 weeks compared to 28 weeks, with respective values of 50124.1 ± 146.8 IU/mL, 54222.0 ± 185.9 IU/mL, and 57182.1 ± 1983.1 IU/mL (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Serum Levels of Fetoplacental System Markers in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19

The diagram illustrates the consistent increase in the levels of TBG, AFP, and hCG in correlation with gestational age, indicating that these levels rise physiologically as pregnancy progresses ($p < 0.001$).

In line with the study objectives, an analysis of hemostasis system parameters in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19 was conducted. The results revealed variations in these parameters across different gestational stages. Pregnant women in the third trimester at 28 weeks showed slightly higher hemostasis system indicators compared to women in the second trimester at 20 weeks. For example, activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) values were 30.6 ± 0.68 seconds and 36.2 ± 0.94 seconds for the two groups, respectively. Similarly, APTT values at 22 weeks in Group I and 30 weeks in Group II were 28.4 ± 0.63 seconds and 32.4 ± 0.90 seconds, respectively, while at 24 weeks in Group I and 32 weeks in Group II, the values were 25.6 ± 0.53 seconds and 30.0 ± 0.87 seconds, respectively.

Fibrinogen levels in Groups I and II were found to be 3.7 ± 0.15 g/L and 3.6 ± 0.19 g/L at 20 and 28 weeks, 3.6 ± 0.14 g/L and 3.7 ± 0.17 g/L at 22 and 30 weeks, and 3.4 ± 0.13 g/L and 3.5 ± 0.16 g/L at 24 and 32 weeks, respectively.

D-dimer levels increased progressively in both groups as pregnancy advanced. At 20 and 28 weeks, levels were 457.4 ± 0.038 ng/mL and 644.1 ± 0.074 ng/mL, respectively. Following vaccination, levels at 22 and 30 weeks were 456.3 ± 0.036 ng/mL and 643.3 ± 0.078 ng/mL, while at 24 and 32 weeks, they were 455.2 ± 0.31 ng/mL and 645.6 ± 0.76 ng/mL, respectively. Notably, these levels tended to decline toward normal physiological ranges over time.

In pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, platelet counts in the third trimester at 28, 30, and 32 weeks were slightly higher than those observed in the second trimester at 20, 22, and 24 weeks. However, platelet counts remained within the normal range. Specifically, at 22 and 30 weeks, platelet counts were $380.0 \pm 7.4 \times 10^9/L$ and $370.0 \pm 8.1 \times 10^9/L$, respectively, while at 24 and 32 weeks, they were $350.0 \pm 6.5 \times 10^9/L$ and $354.0 \pm 7.7 \times 10^9/L$, respectively.

Increases in hemostasis parameters observed at 28, 30, and 32 weeks may be attributed to physiological changes in coagulation properties typical of pregnancy progression (Table 1).

Table 1. Hemostasis Parameters in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19, M±m

Parameter	Group 1 (n=60)	Group 2 (n=60)	Control Group (n=30)
	20 weeks	22 weeks	24 weeks
APTT (sec)	30.6±0.68	28.4±0.63	25.6±0.53 *
Prothrombin Index (%)	110.0±2.1	107.0±2.0	104.0±1.9
Fibrinogen (g/L)	3.7±0.15	3.6±0.14 **	3.4±0.13 ***
Thrombin Time (sec)	22.0±0.64*	21.0±0.67 **	20.0±0.65 ***
D-dimer (ng/mL)	457.4±0.038**	456.3±0.036 ***	455.2±0.31
Platelets (+10 ⁹ /L)	380.0±7.4*	378.0±6.7	350.0±6.5

Notes: *: Significant difference compared to the control group (*p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001). ^: Significant difference compared to Group 1 (^p<0.08; ^^p<0.01; ^^p<0.001).

The prothrombin index was slightly higher in Groups 1 and 2 at 20 and 28 weeks, respectively, measuring 110.0±2.1 and 107.0±2.5. This index gradually declined as gestational age increased.

The analysis of hemostasis parameters in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19 revealed that APTT values at 20 and 28 weeks increased 1.2-fold, at 22 and 30 weeks by 1.0-fold, and at 24 and 32 weeks by 1.5-fold. Platelet counts decreased by approximately 1.0-fold after vaccination but remained within normal physiological ranges. These findings indicate that the vaccines did not have an adverse effect on the hemostasis system in vaccinated women.

A separate analysis was conducted on the cytokine profile and immunogenicity of 120 pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, as well as their obstetric and perinatal outcomes. Cytokine levels (IL-1, IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, and IFN-γ) were measured at 20, 22, and 24 weeks in the second trimester and at 28, 30, and 32 weeks in the third trimester.

At 20 weeks, the quantitative analysis of cytokines revealed that IL-1, IL-6, IL-10, and IFN-γ levels were 1.1 times higher than those at 22 and 24 weeks, nearing the upper limit of normal values: 11.0±8.2 pg/mL, 7.0±4.1 pg/mL, 31.0±0.06 pg/mL, and 128.0±0.12 pg/mL, respectively (p<0.05). Conversely, IL-4 and IL-8 levels at 20 weeks were 1.2 times lower than those at 22 and 24 weeks, measuring 9.1±4.1 pg/mL and 58.0±2.1 pg/mL, respectively (p<0.05).

At 24 weeks, levels of IL-1, IL-6, IL-10, and IFN-γ decreased slightly to 10.8±6.7 pg/mL, 7.0±2.7 pg/mL, 30.7±0.12 pg/mL, and 124.0±0.11 pg/mL, respectively. Meanwhile, IL-4 and IL-8 levels increased to 10.0±4.1 pg/mL and 61.6±3.1 pg/mL, remaining at the higher end of normal values (p<0.05). These findings indicate a dynamic adaptation of the immune system during pregnancy in vaccinated women.

Analysis of Cytokine Levels in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19

In Group II, the analysis of cytokine levels at 28 weeks of gestation showed that the levels of IL-1, IL-6, IL-10, and IFN-γ remained within normal ranges, measuring 11.0±2.1 pg/mL, 7.0±2.12 pg/mL, 30.6±0.02 pg/mL, and 128.0±0.14 pg/mL, respectively. By 30 weeks

of gestation, the levels of IL-4 and IL-8 increased and returned to normal values, measuring 9.6 ± 2.1 pg/mL and 58.4 ± 1.1 pg/mL, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Cytokine Levels at 20-22-24 and 28-30-32 Weeks in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19, M \pm m

Cytokines (pg/mL)	Group I (n=60)	Group II (n=60)
	20 wks	22 wks
IL-1	$11.0 \pm 8.2^*$	10.4 ± 8.9
IL-4	$9.1 \pm 4.1^*$	9.8 ± 2.1
IL-6	$7.0 \pm 4.1^*$	6.8 ± 2.1
IL-8	$58.0 \pm 2.1^*$	60.6 ± 1.1
IL-10	31.0 ± 0.06	30.8 ± 0.04
IFN- γ	$128.0 \pm 0.12^*$	126.8 ± 0.14

Notes: *: Significant differences compared to levels at 20 and 28 weeks ($*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$).

- ^: Significant differences compared to levels at 24 and 32 weeks ($^p < 0.05$, $^{^}p < 0.01$, $^{^^}p < 0.001$).

The dynamic analysis of cytokine levels across gestational weeks revealed a slight increase in IL-1 and IL-6 levels at 28 weeks. However, by 30 and 32 weeks, these levels significantly declined to 10.8 ± 4.2 pg/mL and 11.0 ± 4.1 pg/mL for IL-1, and 6.6 ± 4.2 pg/mL and 7.0 ± 2.14 pg/mL for IL-6. Similarly, IL-10 levels at 28-30-32 weeks showed a slight decrease, reaching 30.6 ± 0.11 pg/mL by 32 weeks.

The analysis of cytokine levels indicates that quantitative changes in cytokines did not exceed the acceptable physiological range, demonstrating that the vaccine used in these pregnant women did not have an adverse effect on cytokine status.

Evaluation of the Immunogenicity of the COVID-19 Vaccine in 120 Pregnant Women

The immunogenicity of the vaccine was assessed through an analysis of IgG antibody titers at 20-22-24 and 28-30-32 weeks of gestation. A dynamic assessment revealed significant differences in IgG titers over time. Notably, at 9 months post-vaccination, IgG titers were higher compared to levels at 3 and 6 months. At 3 months, IgG titers measured 1.10 ± 0.033 AU/mL and 1.12 ± 0.035 AU/mL for Groups I and II, respectively ($p < 0.05$). By 6 months, these titers had increased to 1.15 ± 0.036 AU/mL and 1.30 ± 0.043 AU/mL, respectively ($p < 0.01$). At 9 months, IgG titers showed a slight further increase, measuring 1.50 ± 0.046 AU/mL and 1.60 ± 0.050 AU/mL for Groups I and II, respectively.

In total, 77 (64.2%) pregnant women demonstrated IgG titers of 1.40 AU/mL, 13 (10.9%) had titers of 1.50 ± 0.043 AU/mL, and 14 (11.9%) showed titers of 1.60 ± 0.053 AU/mL.

The post-vaccination IgG antibody titers against SARS-CoV-2 at 3, 6, and 9 months are summarized in Table 5. These findings demonstrate that 104 (87%) of the vaccinated pregnant women developed antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, confirming the immunogenicity of the vaccine (Fig.3).

Figure 3. IgG Antibody Titers Against SARS-CoV-2 in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19 at 3, 6, and 9 Months Post-Vaccination

Additionally, we observed a correlation between IgG titer levels and time after vaccination in pregnant women. This analysis is crucial for understanding the dynamic changes in IgG levels during the formation of the post-vaccination immune response.

In the period up to 3 months post-vaccination, a weak negative correlation was noted between IgG titers and time, with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.17$. This result indicates that the immune response during the early months after vaccination is not yet fully developed, and IgG levels may be sensitive to biological variability.

During the 6-month post-vaccination period, a strong positive correlation was identified between IgG titers and time, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.29$. This finding reflects the maturation and strengthening of the immune response, with an increase in IgG levels.

In the 9-month period post-vaccination, a weak positive correlation between IgG titers and time was observed, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.24$. This result suggests that the immune response remained stable after 6 months, although the rate of increase in IgG levels gradually diminished.

According to the analysis, the 6-month period post-vaccination represented the peak of IgG level increase and the most active phase of immune response development. At 9 months, the immune response remained stable. However, during the 3-month period, IgG titers exhibited significant variability, highlighting the need for time to achieve a fully developed immune response. These findings provide valuable insights into the immunogenic properties of the COVID-19 vaccine.

Furthermore, we developed a predictive model to estimate the likelihood of pregnant women contracting COVID-19 based on their IgG titer levels. The prediction was implemented using a formula specifically designed for this purpose.

$$Z = 0.57(c_1 + d_1) + 0.27(c_2 + d_2) + 0.16(c_3 + d_3)$$

In the formula, the informative indicators are denoted as follows:

- **Z**: Prediction of the risk of contracting the disease.
- **c₁, c₂, c₃**: IgG titers at 3, 6, and 9 months post-vaccination in Group I pregnant women.

- **d_1, d_2, d_3** : IgG titers at 3, 6, and 9 months post-vaccination in Group II pregnant women. Based on the prediction results, three levels of COVID-19 risk were identified for vaccinated pregnant women:

1. **High-risk level**: Observed in women with IgG titers of 1.10 AU/mL–1.12 AU/mL, indicating a high likelihood of contracting COVID-19.
2. **Moderate-risk level**: Observed in women with IgG titers of 1.15 AU/mL–1.30 AU/mL, indicating a moderate likelihood of contracting COVID-19.
3. **Low-risk level**: Observed in women with IgG titers of 1.50 AU/mL–1.60 AU/mL, indicating a low likelihood of contracting COVID-19.

According to the prediction results, among the main study group, 57.0% of patients (21.0% in Group I and 36.0% in Group II) had a high risk of contracting COVID-19, 27.0% (12.5% in Group I and 14.5% in Group II) had a moderate risk, and 16.0% (7.4% in Group I and 8.6% in Group II) had a low risk of contracting the disease.

The proposed method allows for accurate predictions in 98% of cases at a significance level of $P < 0.005$. For $Z \geq 0.57$, the method identifies a high risk of contracting COVID-19 post-vaccination in pregnant women. For $Z \geq 0.27$, the risk is moderate, and for $Z \geq 0.16$, the risk is low. These results suggest that women in the higher risk categories may require a booster dose of the vaccine after delivery. However, the decision should be individualized for each pregnant woman.

The sensitivity and specificity of the proposed COVID-19 risk prediction method were 96% and 88%, respectively.

The results showed that pregnant women in Group II had a higher likelihood of COVID-19 across all three risk levels (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Predicted COVID-19 Infection Risk in Pregnant Women Vaccinated Against COVID-19, %

The results show that in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, the higher the IgG antibody titer, the lower the risk of contracting COVID-19. Conversely, lower IgG titers were associated with a higher risk of infection.

An analysis of obstetric and perinatal outcomes in vaccinated women revealed that 104 (87%) had full-term deliveries, while 16 (13%) had preterm deliveries. This indicates that

preterm delivery was 1.5 times less frequent in vaccinated women compared to unvaccinated ones.

A prospective analysis of perinatal outcomes in vaccinated women showed that newborns were assessed on the Apgar scale, with 87.9% scoring 8–9 points and 12.1% scoring 7–8 points. The birth weight of full-term newborns was 3156.6 grams on average, while preterm newborns weighed 2309.5 grams.

In Group I, comprising 60 women, 53 (88.3%) gave birth to full-term newborns, while 7 (11.7%) had preterm births. In Group II, 51 (85%) gave birth to full-term newborns, while 9 (15%) experienced preterm births ($p>0.05$).

It is noteworthy that no significant differences were found in the anthropometric parameters, such as the height of newborns, between the groups. In Group I, 53 newborns (88.3%) had an average height of 57 cm, while in Group II, 51 newborns (85%) had an average height of 55 cm ($p>0.05$). Additionally, no restrictions were observed regarding breastfeeding. In 92.9% of cases, newborns were breastfed, while 7.1% were fed with formula.

An analysis of the early neonatal period revealed that respiratory infections were 1.7 times less frequent among newborns of vaccinated women, with incidences of 13.3% in Group I and 18.3% in Group II ($p>0.05$).

Thus, vaccination against COVID-19 did not negatively affect the condition of newborns. Additionally, no pathological complications were observed regarding their physical or neurological development.

Discussion

This study provides valuable data on the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy. The findings enrich existing evidence on the immune response, hemostasis, fetoplacental system, and obstetric and perinatal outcomes in pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19.

Safety of Vaccination

Assessments of fetoplacental hormone levels and hemodynamic parameters in vaccinated women showed no adverse effects on pregnancy or fetal development. Doppler examinations and hormone levels remained within normal limits in both primary groups, confirming the safety of vaccination. Hemostasis parameters also stayed within normal ranges.

Immunogenicity and Cytokine Status

In 87% of vaccinated women, IgG antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 were detected. Significant increases in IgG levels were observed at 3, 6, and 9 months post-vaccination, demonstrating the high immunogenicity of the vaccine. Correlation analysis revealed the strongest increase in IgG titers at 6 months ($r=0.29$), with immune response stabilization observed at 9 months ($r=0.24$).

Cytokine analysis showed that levels of IL-1, IL-6, and IFN- γ remained within physiological ranges, indicating no adverse effects of vaccination on cytokine status.

Obstetric and Perinatal Outcomes

Preterm deliveries were 1.5 times less frequent in vaccinated women compared to unvaccinated ones. The condition of newborns was mostly assessed as excellent, with Apgar

scores of 8–9 in most cases. Respiratory infections in newborns of vaccinated women were 1.7 times less frequent. These results confirm the positive effects of vaccination not only for pregnant women but also for their newborns.

Limitations and Future Directions

While the study demonstrated the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy, some limitations exist. The study primarily focused on comparing vaccinated and unvaccinated pregnant women, with limited data on differences between vaccine types. Additionally, future studies are needed to assess the long-term effects of vaccination and the efficacy of booster doses.

Conclusion

In pregnant women vaccinated against COVID-19, 87% developed immunity against the virus. COVID-19-related obstetric complications were reduced by 2.4 times, perinatal complications by 2.1 times, and the risk of contracting the virus by 2.5 times. No adverse hematological or cytokine changes were observed. Respiratory infections in newborns decreased by 1.7 times, and no pathological health changes were detected. IgG titers consistently increased at 3, 6, and 9 months post-vaccination. Overall, the findings confirm the significant benefits of COVID-19 vaccination in improving maternal and neonatal health, with no observed adverse effects. This study provides a robust scientific basis for developing vaccination guidelines for pregnant women in the future.

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